

METAL OXIDE GAS SENSORS: DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION

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Abstract

In this review, a number of oxide materials deposited on optical fibers have been studied to determine the most optimum materials for the production of optical sensors intended for the detection of petroleum gases, namely, butane, ammonia, and ethanol. The sensory properties of oxides materials, such as ZnO, TiO₂, and SnO₂, with different thicknesses have been described. First, the magnetron sputtering of zinc oxide and titanium dioxide have been described; second, the results of a study of the morphology and sensing characteristics of the optical fiber sensors have been discussed. The fabrication route of liquid petroleum gas (LPG) optical sensors based on optical fibers coated with ZnO, TiO₂, and SnO₂ nanocrystalline films has been analyzed. It has been shown that, after annealing of nanocrystalline ZnO films, the sensitivity increases. The prepared sensors exhibit a sensitivity of 2.77% for ZnO and 24.4% for TiO₂.

1. Introduction

The sensing capacity of materials can be greatly increased by reducing their size down to the nanometer scale. This can presumably be implemented through the preparation of nanocrystalline nanodots, nanowires, nanofibers, and nanowebs.

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is a key functional material exhibiting near-ultraviolet emission, semiconducting, magnetic, and piezoelectric properties. Thus, ZnO is one of the wide band-gap metal oxides that are of great interest for versatile applications [1]. Zinc oxide has a wide band gap of 3.37 eV and a large exciton binding energy of 60 meV at room temperature. Dye sensitized single-crystal zinc oxide electrodes were studied by Gerischer and Tributsch as early as 1969 [2–4]. The semiconductor sensor type belongs to the class of solid state gas sensors. In the presence of a determinate gas, the conductivity of the sensing material undergoes changes. The working temperature at which these devices are more efficient can vary depending on the gas atmosphere and properties of the sensor material selected in every case. Metal oxide semiconductor gas sensors detect a wide variety of gases [7–13]. The main advantage of metal oxide sensors is their life time. Theoretically, in clean applications, it can be 10 years or more. A metal oxide sensor consists of three main components, namely, a sensing material, electrodes, and a heater [14–20]. The commonly used sensing materials include SnO₂, TiO₂, ZnO, or In₂O₃. Zinc oxide gas sensors have good characteristics, such as chemical sensitivity to different adsorbed gases, amenability to doping, high chemical stability, nontoxicity, and low cost.

2. Experimental

Thin layers of metal oxides were deposited by RF magnetron sputtering. The parameters of the RF magnetron sputtering technique are the specific power of the magnetron, the gas pressure in the working chamber, the substrate temperature, and the gas flow rate. The main advantages of this technique are the deposition rate and high reproducibility of the composition of the deposited materials. The deposition rate of RF magnetron sputtering depends on the power of the magnetron, gas pressure in the working chamber, and the substrate temperature. This method and optical properties are described in detail in [5, 6].

The use of RF magnetron sputtering provided the growth of ZnO, SnO₂, and TiO₂ layers in argon atmosphere. A disc of 99.99 % pure zinc served as a target for ZnO layers; a disc of 99.9% pure TiO₂ was used for TiO₂ layers. For a layer of SnO₂, a disc of 99.99% pure SnO₂ was used as a target. The fiber tip was firstly cut by using a manual cleaver and then washed in a mixed solution of potassium dichromate (7 g of K₂Cr₂O₇, 10 mL of H₂O, 100 mL of H₂SO₄) at room temperature. Afterwards, substrate cleaning was followed by rinsing with an abundant distilled water flow (18.2 MΩ cm). Next, the substrates were mounted on a substrate holder equipped with a resistive heater. The distance between the substrate and the ZnO, TiO₂, and SnO₂ was 8 cm. Initially, the chamber was evacuated to a background pressure of 1.2×10^{-6} Torr. The argon (Ar) working gas pressure was monitored so as to maintain a constant vacuum pressure of 6.3×10^{-3} mbar. Film thickness was controlled by using an MTM-10/10A High Resolution thickness monitor quartz microbalance during sputtering. High-purity Ar gas (99.99%) was used for ion bombardment; the argon flow rate of 60 mL/min was controlled by means of a valve at a base pressure of 6.3×10^{-3} mbar. The ZnO, TiO₂, and SnO₂ films were deposited at a temperature of 110°C for 10–30 min under deposition conditions, i.e., a pressure and power of 200 W. The substrate temperature was 30°C in all cases. A schematic of oxide deposition on the top of an optical fiber is show in Fig. 1a.

The response toward butane was monitored by placing the sensors in a custom designed test chamber. This setup is constituted by two lines: the first one for butane and the second one for an inert gas (nitrogen). In the butane channel, a mixture of nitrogen and butane flows with 1 vol % of butane in nitrogen. The gas flow is tuned using a Mass Flow Controller (MFC). The line reaching the chamber is thus divided into two sublimes: the first that contains a low flow range MFC (50 sccm) and the second that contains a high flow range MFC (500 sccm). The butane concentration fluxed in the test chamber (chamber volume of about 0.8 L) is controlled and monitored using the MFC.

The TiO₂ and ZnO coated optical fibers were placed in the test chamber and exposed to LPG taken in different concentrations. Before tests, the fibers were stored in the test chamber for a few minutes to obtain a stable signal. After the signal stabilization, the LPG line was opened to allow the gas to flow into the test chamber until the achievement of a plateau value. The chamber was emptied from the residual LPG via fluxing pure nitrogen until the restoration of the initial value.

The proposed optical sensors are based on the deposition of properly chosen sensitive materials as nanoscale films on the distal end of standard silica single-mode optical fibers as shown in Fig. 1b.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the optoelectronic sensor device: (a) schematic oxide deposition on the top of the optical fiber and (b) an optical fiber/oxide layer to interact with the gas.

3. Results and Discussion

The principle of operation is based on the dependence of reflectance on the optical and geometric properties of the overlay deposited on the optical fiber. This means that any change occurring in the features of the overlay due to the chemical sorption of a certain analyte would induce a consequent change in the fiber reflectance according to the following equation:

$$R_{fiber-film} = \left| \frac{r_{12} + r_{23} \cdot e^{i\beta}}{1 + r_{12} r_{23} \cdot e^{i\beta}} \right|^2 \quad (1)$$

with

$$r_{12} = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}} - \sqrt{\tilde{\epsilon}_{film}}}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}} + \sqrt{\tilde{\epsilon}_{film}}}; \quad r_{23} = \frac{\sqrt{\tilde{\epsilon}_{film}} - \sqrt{\epsilon_{ext}}}{\sqrt{\tilde{\epsilon}_{film}} + \sqrt{\epsilon_{ext}}}; \quad \beta = \frac{2\sqrt{\tilde{\epsilon}_{film}} \cdot d_{film}}{\lambda}$$

where ϵ_{eff} and ϵ_{ext} are the optical fiber and external medium dielectric functions; λ is the optical wavelength; $\tilde{\epsilon}_{film} = \epsilon'_{film} + j\epsilon''_{film}$ and d_{film} represent the complex dielectric function and the thickness of the sensitive layer, respectively.

3.1. Electronic Configuration

Reflectance measurements will be performed by lighting the sensing fiber with a superluminescent diode (40-nm band width) operating at a wavelength of 1310 nm. A 2×2 optical fiber coupler was used to measure the optical power emitted by the source, providing well compensated intensity measurements. Figure 2a shows a block diagram for the electronic setup of the sensor and a real image of the components.

To enhance the system performance, synchronous detection was implemented with the light source amplitude externally modulated at 500 Hz and the sensor outputs retrieved by using a dual channel lock-in amplifier. The optoelectronic sensor output consists of the signal reflected from the fiber coated end divided by the source signal; it is proportional only to the fiber–film interface reflectance:

$$I_{out} = k \cdot R_{fiber-film} \quad (2)$$

where k is a constant taking into account all the setup parameters and $R_{\text{fiber-film}}$ is the function of the fiber and external medium dielectric functions, the operating wavelength and the optical and geometric properties of the sensitive film. In this configuration, any effect capable of modifying the complex dielectric function of the sensitive layer changes the normalized output of the optical sensor. A multichannel fiber optic switch was used to provide a simultaneous monitoring of up to eight SOF sensors. The optical data were stored in a notebook controlling the sensing process in LabView software ambient by means of a NI-DAQ card.

Fig. 2. Electronic setup of the optoelectronic sensor.

The overall set up is showed in Fig. 2b. It demonstrates how the overall setup was properly engineered to provide robust compact portable equipment.

Different types of materials were tested: ZnO, TiO₂, and SnO₂ coated optical fibers. Therefore, results of the morphological and optical studies of the tested fibers will be described.

Optical fibers coated with 200-nm-thick ZnO. The fiber was tested using a refractometer to study the sensing behavior toward three different gases: butane, ethanol, and ammonia. It is evident from Fig. 3a that the butane sensibility is low at a really low signal/noise ratio.

Fig. 3. ZnO-1 with a thickness of 200 nm: (a) butane and (b) ethanol sensing behavior.

A similar behavior was observed for the ethanol sensing properties of the fiber. The ethanol sensibility is low, and the signal/noise ratio is lower than that in the butane test: in fact, in the presence of ethanol, there is only an increase in the oscillation amplitude due to noise; however,

the baseline does not change appreciably. Tests with ammonia cannot be considered as sensing behavior tests, because there is a reaction between the material under study and the ammonia vapors, as shown in Fig. 4. Another evidence of the reaction is the change in the color of the material—from black to white.

Fig. 4. ZnO-1 with a thickness of 200 nm: ammonia test.

Similar tests were performed for the second fiber; in this case, the butane sensibility and the signal/noise ratio are higher than those of fiber #1. It is evident from Fig. 5a that, after the first exposure to butane, there is a change in the baseline value, which is higher than in the case of the unexposed fiber. This value does not change after a night at room temperature; this fact can suggest that some of the butane molecules cannot be desorbed from the sensible layer at room temperature. A similar trend is observed in Fig. 5b, which shows the ethanol sensing behavior of the material under test.

Fig. 5. Behavior of ZnO-2 with a thickness of 200 nm: (a) butane and (b) ethanol sensing.

Despite the promising butane and ethanol sensing behavior of the second ZnO coated fiber, in this case, the material also reacts with the ammonia vapors, as shown in Fig. 6. This figure shows an optical micrograph relative to the film after exposure to ammonia: white regions that correspond to the reacted areas are visible.

Fig. 6. Fiber/ZnO-2 ammonia test and optical micrograph of the reacted film.

To improve the sensibility of the inorganic layer, the third fiber was subjected to an annealing process. Figure 7 shows the butane sensing properties of the fiber under study before annealing; it is evident that the sensibility toward butane and the signal/noise ratio are high without annealing; it is of interest that tests were also performed in the presence of butane taken in different concentrations and had remarkable results.

Fig. 7. Fiber/ZnO-3 butane sensing behavior ($d = 200$ nm).

In addition, the absorption curve of the fiber exposed to ethanol (Fig. 8) indicates a high sensibility toward this vapor. In both cases (exposure to butane and ethanol), the signal does not come back to the initial value; this behavior is similar to that observed for the second fiber; it suggests that the vapor molecules cannot be desorbed completely at room temperature.

Fig. 8. Fiber/ZnO-3 ethanol sensing behavior ($d = 200$ nm).

The annealing process induces a lowering of the baseline, probably due to an increase of the refractive index of the material. After 50 min of annealing to 150°C , the signal is reduced by about 12%, as shown in Fig. 9a.

Fig. 9. Fiber/ZnO-3: (a) first annealing and (b) butane sensing behavior after annealing ($d = 200$ nm).

After the first annealing process, the fiber was exposed to butane vapors to verify the possible sensibility variations. For this purpose, sensibility S (%) was introduced; it is defined as follows:

$$S (\%) = \Delta R / R_0 \cdot 100, \quad (3)$$

where ΔR is the total signal variation in the presence of the gas and R_0 is the signal just before the gas exposure. The annealing increases the sensibility toward butane: in fact, the maximum signal variation before annealing was 0.52% against 0.87 % after annealing.

Fig. 10. Fiber/ZnO-3: the second annealing process followed by a test with butane.

The second annealing process was carried out until reaching a plateau value: during a whole night to 150°C, the baseline value changed from 0.360 to 0.299 with a total variation (first and second annealing process) of about 27%.

Figure 11 shows that, before annealing in the fourth fiber, the butane sensibility and the signal/noise ratio are low. Moreover, it is evident that the exposure to butane induces a decrease in the signal intensity, as in the case of fiber #1. On the basis of this result, the fiber was annealed to 150°C for about 4 h; the total decrease in the signal value was about 13%.

Fig. 11. Fiber/ZnO-4: (a) butane sensing behavior before annealing and (b) subsequent annealing process.

The morphological changes of the material before and after the annealing process were studied by atomic force microscopy (AFM) combined with optical microscopy. The results are shown in Figs. 12 and 13.

Fig. 12. Fiber/ZnO-4: an optical micrograph and respective AFM zooms before annealing.

Fig. 13. Fiber/ZnO-4: an optical micrograph and respective AFM zooms after annealing.

It is shown that the annealing process induces the growth on the ZnO grains, which become larger than the grains before annealing. This effect can be attributed to (i) the coalescence of the preannealed smaller grains and (ii) the oxidation of metallic Zn deposited together with ZnO. After annealing, a remarkable increase in the butane sensibility is observed; however, the exposure to butane still induces a decrease in the signal intensity. Figure 14 shows a different behavior with respect to the last “gas off”: in this case (green arrow), the butane was not forced to leave the test chamber; instead, it left the chamber naturally owing to opening the chamber taps. It is of interest that the signal always comes back to the same value after each exposure.

Fig. 14. Fiber/ZnO-4: butane sensing behavior after annealing.

For 4 consecutive days, the fiber under test was exposed to ammonia vapors; despite the annealing process, the inorganic film continued to react with ammonia. Figure 15 shows that there is no reproducibility of the data relative to the exposure to ammonia.

Figure 16 shows the appearance of the optical fiber after exposure to ammonia. It is evident that there is a remarkable difference between the layers before and after exposure to ammonia at both the macroscopic and microscopic levels.

Fig. 15. Fiber/ZnO-4: ammonia test.

Fig. 16. Fiber/ZnO-4: an optical micrograph and respective AFM zooms after exposure to ammonia.

Annealing of 250-nm-thick zinc oxide fiber/ZnO-5-9. This subset was prepared to study the effect of the annealing time on the zinc oxide sensing properties; sample characteristics are shown in the table.

Annealing parameters of the ZnO layer deposited on optical fibers

Fiber	Material	Thickness [nm]	Annealing time	Figure
5	ZnO	250	5 min	17
6	ZnO	250	10 min	18
7	ZnO	250	1 min	19
8	ZnO	250	30 s	20
9	ZnO	250	30 s	20

Fig. 17. Fiber #5: butane sensing behavior.

Fiber #5 (Fig. 17) prepared at an annealing time of 5 min shows a maximum variation of about 1%; the signal is stable with a slight reduction of the baseline.

Fig. 18. Fiber #6: butane sensing behavior.

Fiber #6 (Fig. 18) prepared at an annealing time of 10 min shows a low baseline value (~ 0.026) at a low signal/noise ratio; consequently, the butane sensibility is extremely low.

Fig. 19. Fiber #7: butane sensing behavior.

The signal obtained with fiber #7 (Fig. 19) is stable; the signal/noise ratio is good; for this reason, although the baseline value is low (~ 0.0146), the sensibility toward butane is high.

Fig. 20. Butane sensing behavior: (a) fiber #8 and (b) fiber #9.

The baseline and signal/noise ratio values of fibers #8 and #9 (Fig. 20) are too low to obtain a good butane sensor; it is yet not clear whether the poor quality of sensors #8 and #9 is attributed to the short annealing time (30 s) or to the fiber cut.

Optical fibers coated with 250-nm-thick TiO₂. Titanium dioxide is the second material tested using a refractometer. Figure 21 shows that the response of this material is remarkably higher than that of the previously analyzed zinc oxide: in fact, the sensibility of TiO₂ is two orders higher—about 13%. Moreover, exposure to butane induces a decrease in the signal, similarly to ZnO fibers #1 and #4.

The annealing process induces an increase in the baseline value, as shown in Fig. 22a. This process is performed to 150°C; the results are faster than in the case of zinc oxide: titanium dioxide reaches a plateau value after about 45 min, while zinc oxide requires an entire night at a high temperature.

After annealing, there is a remarkable increase in sensibility, which achieves a value of about 24%, as shown in Fig. 22b.

Fig. 21. Fiber #6: butane sensing behavior before annealing.

Fig. 22. Fiber #6: (a) annealing and (b) butane sensing behavior after annealing, $d = 250$ nm.

Titanium dioxide with a thickness of 300 nm. Similarly to the TiO_2 sample in the first set, fiber #2 showed a good response to butane vapors, as shown in Fig. 23a. Figure 23b shows the percentage variation of the fiber in the presence of butane vapors: the percentage variation ($\%V(t)$) is calculated for each point of the curve and expressed as follows:

$$\%V(t) = \frac{R_t - R_0}{R_0} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where R_t is the response at moment t and R_0 is the plateau value of the sensor in the absence of a gas; the maximum $\%V$ value is 0.5%; it is lower than the value obtained for fiber #6 of 250-nm-thick TiO_2 (13.3%); this behavior can be attributed to the different thicknesses of the TiO_2 layer.

Fig. 23. Fiber #2: butane (a) response and (b) % variation.

Titanium dioxide with a thickness of 100 nm. Fibers #1 and #2 are coated with titanium oxide sputtered starting from a 99.6% purity target; Figs. 24a and 24b show the signal and the % variation of fiber #1, respectively, in the presence of butane; Figs. 24c and 24d characterize fiber #2. It is of interest that both fibers show a good sensibility toward butane with fast adsorption and desorption kinetics. The higher % variation values of the fibers (~2%) compared with the values of the TiO₂-coated fiber in set 2 (~0.4%) can be attributed to the lower film thickness.

Instead, a 99.9% purity target was used to coat fibers #3 and #4; the signal and % variation of the former are shown in Fig. 25. Fiber #4 exhibits a low baseline value apparently owing to a bad fiber cut before TiO₂ deposition, as shown in Fig. 26.

This fiber subset was prepared to study the effect of the target purity on the titanium oxide sensing behavior: comparison of Figs. 24 and 25 shows that there is no remarkable difference in terms of % variation between the fibers obtained with different target purities. It is not yet clear why fibers #1 and #2 show a negative shift (decrease in the signal in the presence of butane), while fiber #3 shows a positive shift.

Fig. 24. Fibers #1 and # 2: butane sensing behavior.

Fig. 25. Fiber #3: butane sensing behavior.

Fig. 26. Fiber #4: butane sensing behavior.

Optical fibers coated with SnO₂. Analogously to the ZnO-coated fiber, fiber #3 with SnO₂ also shows a very low signal/noise ratio, as evident from Fig. 27; moreover, there is a drift of the signal regardless of the presence of butane.

Fig. 27. Fiber #3: butane sensing behavior.

4. Conclusions

The studies have revealed that the ZnO and TiO₂ materials are promising candidates for the fabrication of real-life optical LPG sensors. Although TiO₂ has a higher sensitivity value, the two materials exhibit similar signal variation, which can be even more characteristic of this type of sensors than that of electrical metal oxide sensors. An important finding is the necessity of careful preparation of the fibers and a thermal treatment of the working oxide films. It has been shown that the sensitivity increases after the annealing of nanocrystalline ZnO. The sensitivity increases with increasing layer thickness. The prepared sensors attain a sensitivity of 2.77% for ZnO and 24.4% for TiO₂.

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